

Policy Brief #3

Aligning grassroots initiatives and institutional support for a just and inclusive Green Deal

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The Green Deal was designed to mark a transformative moment for Europe. However, its success depends not only on environmental ambitions, but also on social inclusivity. ACCTING addresses the social dimension of the transition aimed for in the Green Deal, focusing on groups historically marginalised in policy processes. These include low-income populations, women and non-binary people, migrants, youth and old adults, and those living in deprived neighbourhoods and rural underserved regions.

This Policy Brief summarises the evidence and analysis of the project's report on second cycle experimental studies and outcomes of its pilot actions, along with concrete recommendations for policymakers to address inequalities produced in the contexts of Green Deal interventions. ACCTING's research and experiments reveal that to effectively address behaviour change and sustainability, **policies need to strengthen collaboration between politics and civil society organisations more, and take into consideration community-based approaches, the weight of collective influence, while addressing systemic inequalities and power dynamics.**

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Insights and recommendations

1. Empower local and community-led sustainability initiatives

A key insight across all ACCTING's research is the significance of local and community-based approaches in fostering sustainable and equitable transformations. Whether in disaster preparedness, biodiversity protection, energy transition, micro-entrepreneurship, food security, sustainable food values, cycling initiatives or car-free policies, the research highlights that change is most effective when it is driven by and for local communities.

Community meeting within the 'Dialogue & Action Against Wildfires' project, © Dock

Community-driven change works

When communities lead sustainability initiatives the outcomes are more trusted, inclusive, and tailored to real needs. Local ownership builds social trust and ensures interventions reflect local values, identities, and lived experiences. It also allows for better adaptation to regional, cultural, and environmental conditions.

But support structures are essential

Despite their potential, community-based efforts cannot thrive without enabling environments. Long-term success requires sustained institutional and financial support from local and national governments. Many initiatives face burnout, underfunding, or marginalisation without these supports, even when they are socially impactful.

The role of institutional support in community-led initiatives: examples from ACCTING pilots

- [Dialogue & Action Against Wildfires](#) (Greece): Village committees co-designed fire preparedness plans based on local knowledge, improving disaster resilience while demonstrating the significance of hands-on, scenario-based learning for driving behavioural change in local communities.
- [Echoversity](#) (Greece): Revived awareness of traditional transhumance practices and their role in biodiversity protection, linking cultural heritage with environmental sustainability. Its bottom-up approach also ensured that the project was relevant and adaptable to evolving community needs.
- [Mapko Connects Community Gardens](#) (Czech Republic): Fosters urban gardening through an online platform, enabling social connection, economic resilience, and shared environmental care. However, many gardens struggle to secure operational permissions from municipalities, or face displacement due to real estate development.

The examples highlight the need for communities to be empowered *and supported by public institutions*, in order to not only implement solutions but also help reshape the systems around them.

1. Institutionalise long-term support for community Initiatives

Funders should provide stable, multi-year funding streams for grassroots sustainability projects, such as food sovereignty efforts, cycling initiatives, energy communities, and urban greening. Create low-barrier funding schemes that are accessible to small, informal or volunteer-based groups, not just registered organisations.

2. Create pathways for community-institution integration

Policies must enable community initiatives to connect with formal institutions, influence decision-making, and scale impact. This requires public bodies to actively partner with community actors through co-governance mechanisms, inclusive funding structures, and integrated planning.

3. Value and embed local knowledge in policy

Local knowledge, especially from marginalised communities, is a critical resource for sustainability. Authorities should recognise it as a real expertise and valid basis for planning and embed it into institutional processes. Participatory governance models must go beyond consultation and give communities real influence over decisions.

4. Support collective urban spaces for participation

In urban contexts, cities should develop and protect spaces for collective governance where citizens can engage in themes they care deeply about, such as cycling, food, or green infrastructure. These spaces are essential for building community, sustaining engagement, and ensuring diverse participation.

5. Invest in digital infrastructure for local collaboration

Support existing and new digital platforms that can facilitate community collaboration. These tools enable knowledge exchange, visibility, and mutual support across local initiatives. They are especially useful for connecting dispersed actors and common goals.

Mapko Community meeting - Map of community gardens © Kokoza

2. Align infrastructure and policy with social justice and community realities

Across the ACCTING research, inadequate infrastructure, restrictive regulations, and structural inequalities consistently emerge as major barriers to sustainability. Physical and institutional frameworks determine whether and who can engage in sustainable practices. Even the most motivated communities struggle to act sustainably when they lack access to energy-efficient housing, renewable energy systems, urban gardens, accessible farmers markets, safe cycling paths, and functional and affordable public transport.

Structures shape possibility

Individuals from disadvantaged groups often face affordability constraints, time poverty, and safety concerns that prevent them from accessing sustainable options, despite strong willingness to engage. The gap between sustainable aspirations and structural conditions is where policy must intervene - providing viable alternatives and addressing structural exclusions.

Aligning infrastructure and policy with community needs: examples from ACCTING pilots

ACCTING pilot actions demonstrate that for sustainability efforts to become not just viable, but inclusive, scalable, and enduring, infrastructure, regulation, and institutional support must align with community needs.

- [Supporting Roma micro-entrepreneurs towards better environmental sustainability](#) (Albania): Culturally sensitive mentoring helped Roma entrepreneurs overcome structural reluctance to formalisation and access resources for sustainable business practices, highlighting how regulatory systems can be made more inclusive.
- [Food4Schools](#) (Greece): A collaborative school-based food programme tackled access and sustainability by providing affordable, nutritious food to low-income families. The initiative led to a Local Action Plan co-developed with the municipality of Thessaloniki and resulted in the creation of the Thessaloniki Food Council, showing how grassroots action can shape formal policy structures and institutionalise long-term change.
- [Edu Move](#) (Albania): A participatory cycling campaign promoted sustainable mobility among youth. Its success depended not only on local engagement but also on political backing and investment in safe cycling infrastructure, demonstrating that behavioural initiatives require institutional support to achieve real impact.
- [Premios inclusivECs: impulsando comunidades inclusivas](#) (Spain): A pilot award project for inclusive energy communities found that, despite strong local interest, outdated decentralised energy regulations blocked implementation. The project underscored the need for flexible policy frameworks to enable grassroots-led energy transitions.

Micro-entrepreneur in Albania,
© IRCA

1. Rebalance responsibility between individuals and institutions

Current policy often focuses on individuals to make the 'right' choices, while structural barriers remain untouched. Governments must shift focus from nudging individual change to removing the systemic constraints that prevent it. This includes redirecting subsidies, reforming planning laws, and creating equity-based funding frameworks that reflect lived inequalities.

2. Invest in inclusive, enabling infrastructure

Governments must fund and prioritise physical infrastructure that makes sustainability possible for all, such as safe cycling networks, accessible public transport, energy-efficient housing, local farmers markets, and spaces for urban food production. These are not secondary to climate action but essential foundations. Investments must be targeted to areas and groups most affected by structural exclusion, including women, migrants, rural populations, and low-income households.

3. Align sustainability policies with affordability and feasibility

Policies that restrict high-emission behaviours, like car-free zones, meat taxes, or biodiversity-related land-use rules, are much needed, but they must be paired with affordable and viable alternatives. Without this, they risk triggering backlash or deepening inequality. Every environmental policy needs to be assessed for its economic and social accessibility, especially for vulnerable groups.

4. Embed intersectional impact assessments in all sustainability policies

Green transition measures must be evaluated to consider environmental outcomes and who benefits or bears the costs. Considerations such as gender+, disability, migration, and socio-economic status need to be mainstreamed into all impact assessments of funded programmes.

5. Make policy and regulation work for small-scale and local actors

Regulatory systems often reflect the priorities of large institutions and actors. Policies must be reformed to accommodate energy communities, micro-entrepreneurs, and food cooperatives, offering clear guidance, simplified administrative pathways, and funding mechanisms accessible to smaller initiatives. When grassroots actors face bureaucratic or legal obstacles, innovation and engagement stall.

6. Hold powerful actors accountable in sustainability transitions

Resistance to environmental policies often stems not from disadvantaged groups, but from privileged actors defending existing advantages. Climate justice demands that political and economic elites, who account for disproportionate emissions, are held to higher standards. Equity in transition means shared goals but differentiated responsibilities.

3. Leverage social networks and collective influence to drive behavioural shifts

ACCTING research across all domains shows that individuals are far more likely to adopt and maintain environmentally sustainable behaviours when they are embedded in strong social networks. The presence of strong social ties also consistently emerges as an enabler of social change. Social networks serve multiple functions: they provide exchange of knowledge and motivation, access to resources, skills, and a shared sense of purpose, skills, and a sense of community and value.

Behaviour is social

Sustainability is not just a matter of personal motivation, knowledge, or financial incentives. It is deeply embedded in social dynamics: what peers encourage, what communities value, and what norms are seen as acceptable. Social networks provide moral support, resources, informal knowledge, role models, and collective momentum. Participation in community-led food or cycling initiatives, for instance, consistently reshapes both personal habits and shared values. Environmental entrepreneurs who are networked into sustainability ecosystems succeed at higher rates than those acting alone.

But current social norms and structures act as barriers

Entrenched cultural practices, gender roles, and lack of social appreciation of environmental sustainability limit participation in activities. Different environmental impacts and engagement possibilities across social classes create power imbalances, resistance, and opposition. Resistance to car-free policies and plant-based diets, or challenges to women cycling in public, show that without collective buy-in and accountability, even the most well-designed policies face backlash or indifference. Thus, policies must both build on enabling social structures, solidarity, and challenge those norms and structures that hinder change.

When people shape practice together: examples from ACCTING pilots

- [*Todas en bici*](#) (Spain): this cycling initiative linked sustainability to social justice by creating inclusive, women-led cycling spaces in low-income neighbourhoods. It empowered women and migrants not only to shift transport habits, but also to reshape local norms around mobility, visibility, and public space use – showing how social connection and safe spaces can drive both environmental and social change.
- [*Uključi se! / Get Involved!*](#) (Serbia): By creating a digital platform to connect volunteers with grassroots environmental projects, this initiative normalised participation in environmental action and expanded access beyond traditional activist spaces. It highlights how digital infrastructure can be leveraged to activate new social norms around collective responsibility and inclusive environmental engagement.
- [*School Goes Green*](#) (Italy): Bringing high school students as volunteers to local sustainability organisations, the project has integrated environmental action into school life and peer networks, fostering youth engagement and reframes sustainability as part of collective identity and civic responsibility.

Get Involved!

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These examples demonstrate that when policies invest in social infrastructure and support inclusive collective action, they can contribute to behavioural change *and* help rewrite the social norms that define what is possible, desirable, and fair in a sustainable society.

1. Invest in social infrastructure for sustainability

Support the development of community centres, advocacy groups, cycling hubs, and food cooperatives as places where people can meet, collaborate, and share environmentally sustainable practices. Public investment in these spaces creates conditions for behavioural change at scale, especially when targeted toward underserved communities.

2. Design interventions that strengthen and diversify social networks

Sustainability policies can build on existing community structures to maximise their reach and impact. By supporting inclusive initiatives in collective spaces and peer-based learning environments such as schools, libraries, and religious institutions, trust, engagement, and access to resources can be built particularly effectively.

3. Empower socially embedded actors as change agents

Entrepreneurs, teachers, community organisers, and volunteers already embedded in local networks can play a catalytic role. Policies should equip them with the tools, funding, and training to lead sustainability efforts in ways that reflect local realities and relational dynamics.

4. Engage, regulate, and hold accountable those with greater decision-making power

Sustainable transitions require collaboration across social classes, where all, also those with power and privilege, are required to change behaviours and contribute to systemic solutions. Policies and initiatives need to more proactively bridge the gap between different social groups, actively promoting cross-group engagement and fostering solidarity rather than deepening social divides and resentment.

5. Use communication strategies that target norms, not just individuals

Public campaigns need to focus on making sustainable behaviours visible, aspirational, and socially rewarded. Messaging that resonates with shared values, such as fairness, care, or community pride, is more likely to shift norms than technical arguments or moral pressure.

6. Reorient political narratives to reflect and shape sustainable norms

Public institutions actively shape social norms through what they fund, regulate, promote, and symbolically endorse. To enable behavioural shifts, policies and political leadership must carry and live according to narratives that normalise sustainability and challenge outdated assumptions (e.g., that car ownership equals freedom, or that cycling is unsafe for women). This requires aligning laws, communications, and investments with a vision of sustainable living as modern, inclusive, and aspirational.

Conclusion

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The ACCTING project offers empirical insight and grounded solutions to inform policy at all levels. By connecting behavioural science, intersectional research, and community practice, it provides a roadmap for integrating a more socially just, equitable, and environmentally sustainable future. Its findings make clear that **environmental and social sustainability are inseparable and must be addressed through coordinated, cross-sectoral strategies** that centre both structural change and lived experience.

A key takeaway is that **sustainable transformation grows from the alignment of grassroots initiative and institutional support, of enabling infrastructure and inclusive governance**. Community-led efforts flourish when backed by policy frameworks that are responsive, redistributive, and rooted in equity. **Their synergies can drive meaningful and inclusive change** across different sustainability domains particularly well.

Inclusivity in the European Green Deal is the foundation of its legitimacy and success, whereas exclusion creates resistance, reinforces inequality, and undermines legitimacy. This means embedding gender+, disability, migration, age, and socio-economic considerations into every level of green policymaking, not as add-ons, but as core design principles. Only by centring those most affected by environmental and social injustice, we can build transitions that are effective, socially just, resilient, and truly transformative.

Further reading from ACCTING

All project outputs available as open access are on the [ACCTING Community on Zenodo](#):

- Zorell, C., Strid, S., & ACCTING consortium. (2023). For an Inclusive and Socially Just European Green Deal: Integrating Gendered and Intersectional Perspectives in Green Deal policies: Policy Brief #1. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078909>
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The ACCTING project

It is acknowledged by now that the global climate crisis is not only an ecological crisis but also an economic, social and political crisis, with devastating effects on individuals and societies. These negative effects are not evenly distributed within societies. It is the poorer, marginalised and vulnerable groups who are the most acutely affected, exacerbating existing socio-economic inequalities. The European Green Deal foresees efficient use of resources for a circular and clean economy. However, inequalities emerge in the context of its policy and interventions.

The EU-funded ACCTING project took these considerations as a starting point for a complex series of research and experimental activities aimed at identifying, analysing and testing policies and initiatives capable of responding to this crisis, mitigating its effects on the most vulnerable and helping them play a significant role in the pursuit of greater environmental sustainability. It explored the impact of Green Deal policy initiatives on individual and collective behaviours, providing evidence, empowering policy-makers and stakeholders to anticipate policy responses and potential negative influences, and mitigate such impacts in decision-making.

The ACCTING project is structured around eight thematic research lines, aligned with the Green Deal policy areas, covering topics from disaster resilience to energy communities, sustainable mobility, food systems, and entrepreneurship. Its research methodology was based on an extensive mapping and analysis of bottom-up initiatives and societal responses to the European Green Deal, narrative interviews, and experimental studies, including case studies, interviews, surveys, and field observations. Findings from these eight thematic research lines informed the co-creation of a set of policy recommendations, two research agendas, and ten pilot actions. These pilot actions centred on ideas for behavioural solutions designed based on project insights, and they were set up to test the transformative potential of these ideas in real-world conditions on sites across Europe. Key aspects defining the pilot actions were participatory design, social inclusion, and local relevance. This integration of research and action ensures both conceptual depth and practical applicability to reduce or prevent policy-related inequalities and advance behavioural change for an inclusive and equal European Green Deal.

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- To find out more: <https://accting.eu> and <https://www.linkedin.com/company/accting>

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